

Dinuclear Diacetylazinedioximato Metal Chelates of Cobalt (II), Palladium(II) and Manganese(II)

Antiferromagnetic Spin-coupling in Low Spin Cobalt(II) and Medium Spin Manganese(II) Dimers

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Dinuclear diacetylazinedioximato metal chelates of cobalt(II), manganese(II) and palladium(II) have been prepared. I.R. spectra suggest that diacetylazinedioximate ion is coordinated to Co(II), Mn(II) and Pd(II) in a bi-bidentate manner. The palladium complex is diamagnetic and is believed to be a dinuclear square planar complex. Its electronic spectra show the characteristic features of palladium(II) square planar complexes. Magnetic susceptibility values for cobalt(II) and manganese(II) complexes at room temperature, correspond to one and three unpaired electrons respectively and suggest planar structure about the metal ions. Susceptibility values over the range of temperature 300°-80°K exhibit antiferromagnetic exchange interactions.

STUDIES on metal complexes with bi-bidentate ligands are very much in vogue during recent years because of their novel stereochemical features and magnetic properties¹⁻⁷. We have reported the diacetylazinedioximato metal chelates of Cu(II) and Ni(II) and have shown that the ligand acts as a bi-bidentate ligand towards two metal ions⁶. Magnetic studies have revealed spin-spin interaction between pairs of metal ions bridged by the conjugated ligand.

In continuation of our interest in this field we have studied the diacetylazinedioximato metal chelates of Co(II), Mn(II) and Pd(II) and the results of the investigation are reported here. The palladium complex is diamagnetic and its electronic spectra resemble the important features of square planar Pd(II) complexes. The manganese complex shows some novel features of interest. At room temperature, its magnetic susceptibility value closely corresponds to the value for three unpaired electrons instead of five usually observed for manganese(II) complexes and imply a planar environment for manganese(II) ions. Its susceptibility values over a range of temperature show the presence of antiferromagnetic interaction between a pair of manganese(II) ions. The magnetic moment of 2.95 B.M. for the cobalt(II) complex also implies a planar configuration.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or E.Merck quality.

1. *Diacetylazinedioxime* was prepared as reported earlier⁶. M.P. found 220° (Literature value 220°).

2. *Bis-(diacetylazinedioximato) dicobalt(II)*: A solution of cobalt acetate tetrahydrate (0.4 g) in about 25 ml of dimethyl formamide was added dropwise with constant stirring to a solution of diacetylazinedioxime (0.4 g) in about 10 ml. of dimethylformamide. As each drop of the cobalt salt solution fell on the ligand solution, the latter solution became red and the colour gradually deepened. Ultimately a dark red viscous liquid was obtained. It was allowed to stand for 15 min. Then solvent ether (200 ml) was added with thorough stirring. A brown red solid appeared and settled down. It was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuo.

Analysis: Found: Co, 22.47; N, 21.82. Calc. for Co₂(DAADO)₂; Co, 23.12; N, 22.0%.

3. *Bis-(diacetylazinedioximato) dimanganese(II)*: Diacetylazinedioxime (0.5 g) was dissolved in the minimum amount of dilute sodium hydroxide solution and a clear pale yellow solution was obtained. The slight excess of the alkali which was present in solution, was neutralised by adding to it a very dilute solution of acetic acid drop by drop with constant stirring. The addition of acid was continued till a faint permanent turbidity was obtained in the solution. The solution was filtered through gooch crucible and the clear filtrate was collected. A warm aqueous solution of manganese nitrate (0.42 g) was added dropwise to the above ligand solution. An yellowish brown solid immediately formed and settled down. It was filtered after 15 min,

washed thoroughly with water followed by rectified spirit and dried in vacuo.

The greyish brown product was analysed.

Analysis : Found : Mn, 21.22; N, 22.0. Calc. for Mn(DAADO)₂, Mn, 21.9; N, 22.3%.

4. *Bis-(diacetylazine-dioximato) dipalladium(II)* : The ligand solution (0.3 g) was prepared as in the case of Mn(II). To this solution, aqueous solution of palladium nitrate (0.35 g in 40 ml. of water) was added. As each drop of the palladium salt came in contact with the ligand solution, an yellowish solid appeared, but it dissolved on shaking. After the addition was over, the solution was concentrated over a hot water bath till the volume reduced to about 30 ml. when some solid was found to have settled down. It was filtered, washed with few ml. of water followed by absolute alcohol and dried in vacuo. The compound was red in colour.

Analysis : Found : Pd, 34.2; N, 18.4. Calc. for Pd(DAADO)₂, Pd, 35.26; N, 18.5%.

Physical measurements :

I.R. spectra were taken in potassium bromide phase. Diffuse reflectance spectra were taken in a Beckmann D.U. spectrophotometer. Magnesium oxide was used as a reference material.

Magnetic measurements were made using a Guoy balance as reported earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

I.R. spectra :

The infrared spectral data of diacetylazinedioxime and its metal chelates with Co(II), Mn(II) and Pd(II) are recorded in Table 1. The basis of assignment of the bands have been discussed earlier⁶. The vibrational spectra of the complexes resemble each other and also the spectra of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes. It is therefore believed that they possess structures analogous to each other and similar to Cu(II) and Ni(II) complex wherein the ligand acts as a bidentate ligand (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Electronic spectra :

The palladium complex is diamagnetic and intensely coloured implying a square planer coordination of the central ion by four nitrogen atoms which is further characterized by electronic spectra rich in absorption bands in the region 600–320 mμ. The spectra show

TABLE 1—STRUCTURALLY IMPORTANT I.R. BANDS OF DIACETYLAZINEDIOXIME AND ITS METAL CHELATES IN CM⁻¹.

	Co ₂ DAADOH ₂ (DAADO) ₂	Mn ₂ (DAADO) ₂	Pd ₂ (DAADO) ₂	Assignments
3125 s, bd 2849 sh	3225	3226 s	3226 s	O-H and C-H stretching
1672	—	—	—	N-OH deformation.
1595 s	1585 m	1580 s	1565 m	C=N stretching
1429 m	1449 s	1440 s	1471 s	C=N stretching
1351 s	1370 m	1360 s	1353 m	CH ₃ deformation
1121 s	1209 w	1120 s	1180 m	CH ₃ rocking
1024 s	1062 w	1035 s	1080 s	
970 s	1010 w	985 s	1010 w	N-O stretching
930 s	960 w	940 s	980 ms	
780 s	865 s	780 s	766 m	
758 m, bd	770 s	750 s	740 m	CH ₃ deformation

s = strong, w = weak, m = medium, bd = broad, sh = shoulder, DAADOH₂ = diacetylazinedioxime.

a broad band at 18,000 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to internal transition within the d-shell of the central metal ion⁸. Another band at 28,000 cm⁻¹ arise from charge transfer and intraligand transitions. The intraligand transitions for diacetylazinedioxime is observed at 28,000 cm⁻¹ and is believed to arise due to π* ← π transition.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of the cobalt(II) complex shows a broad band in the region 20,000 to 29,400 cm⁻¹ and are not well resolved. The broad band represents a combination of band systems associated with d-d transition of Co(II) ion and charge transfer bands. A singular band at 26,300 cm⁻¹ was observed for the manganese(II) complex and seems to be charge transfer in origin.

Magnetic susceptibility :

Magnetic susceptibility of cobalt(II) and manganese(II) complexes has been studied over the temperature range 100–300 °K. Replicate determinations have been carried out on separately prepared samples. The magnetic data are recorded in Table 2. Before we discuss the temperature variation of susceptibility, it is worthwhile to make some observations on the moment observed for these complexes at room temperature.

The magnetic moment observed for the manganese(II) complex at room temperature 3.57 B.M. closely corresponds to three unpaired electrons (spin only moment 3.87 B.M.). Bivalent manganese compounds are known in both spin (S = 5/2) and low spin

($S = 1/2$) states⁹. The high spin complexes possess magnetic moments close to spin only value (5.92 B.M.) and the moments are independent of temperature irrespective of the ligand arrangement whether octahedral or tetrahedral since the ground term is 6A_1 . On the other hand low-spin octahedral complexes lead to a ground term ${}^2T_{2g}$ and should show magnetic moment nearly 2.5 B.M. under the influence of spin orbit coupling constant $\lambda = -300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Available data for low spin complexes range from 1.69 to 2.18 B.M.

of higher orbitally degenerate states such as $(b_{2g})^1 (e_g)^3 (a_{1g})^1$.

The magnetic moment of diacetylazinedioximato manganese(II) complex at room temperature is rather low as compared to square planar Mn(II) phthalocyanine. The lower value is attributed to antiferromagnetic interaction. Temperature variation susceptibility shows fall in magnetic moment as the temperature is lowered. Plot of $\frac{1}{\chi'_m}$ against temperature is linear.

The magnetic data have been treated by taking into consideration a spin-spin interaction of the form $-J \hat{S}_1 \cdot \hat{S}_2$, where S_1 and S_2 are the spins of the manganese(II) ions.¹¹ The molar susceptibility for the dimer with each metal centre having three unpaired spins is given by :

$$\chi'_m = \frac{N\beta^2 g^2}{3kT} \frac{6x^5 + 30x^3 + 84 + N\alpha}{x^6 + 3x^5 + 5x^3 + 7}$$

where $x = e^{J/kT}$.

There is reasonably good agreement in the temperature region 80–260 °K between theoretical and experimental results for $J = -34 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $g = 2$. The negative value of J demonstrates antiferromagnetic interaction between the manganese(II) ions. The exchange process is believed to take place through the π -electron system of the conjugated ligand.

The magnetic data for the cobalt complex are recorded in Table 2 and the susceptibility values lie in the range 2.95–2.81 B.M. within the temperature range 300°–100°K. Magnetic susceptibility of bivalent cobalt(II) compounds have been widely investigated and are found to fall into two classes. In the first, the high spin complexes, μ_{eff} lies in the range 4.3–5.6 B.M. while in the second, the low spin complexes, much smaller values 1.8–2.9 B.M. are found¹². The relation between stereochemistry and magnetic data in high spin complexes has been established on a sound theoretical basis and the conclusions are in good agreement with experimental results. On the otherhand the complexes of the low spin type, have not been examined theoretically and the problem is of considerable difficulty. But available experimental data have been examined which provide a good correlation between stereochemistry and magnetic moment. Such six coordinated low spin complexes are undoubtedly octahedral and four coordinated are believed to be square planar. It is observed that, for complexes believed to be octahedral, the μ_{eff} lies in the range 1.73 to 2.0 B.M. and for complexes regarded as square planar, μ_{eff} lies between 2.1 and 2.9 B.M. The observed moment of 2.95 B.M. for diacetylazinedioximato cobalt(II) thus leads us to believe the compound to be square planar. The moment of the compound slightly falls to 2.72 B.M. at 183°K and θ value is found to be -22°K implying weak antiferromagnetism.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC DATA

Mn ₂ (DAADO) ₂ , $\theta = 125^\circ\text{K}$ $J = -34 \text{ cm}^{-1}$			Co ₂ (DAADO) ₂ , $\theta = -22^\circ\text{K}$		
Temp. °K	$\chi'_{m/2}$ c.g.s., e.m.u.	μ_{eff} B.M.	Temp. °K	$\chi'_{m/2}$ c.g.s., e.m.u.	μ_{eff} B.M.
303.5	5236	3.57	302	3610	2.95
288	5267	3.49	287	3804	2.95
273	5501	3.46	276	3959	2.95
260	5547	3.40	261	4037	2.92
247	5624	3.32	251	4293	2.92
236	5594	3.24	242	4348	2.89
203	5937	3.12	228	4526	2.86
185	6249	3.04	210	4736	2.82
167	7551	2.93	183	5085	2.72
98	9676	2.75	173	6050	2.86
			139	6793	2.75
			115	8773	2.81

The magnetic data of the diacetylazinedioximato manganese(II) complex imply the structure of the complex to be square planar as in the case of manganese phthalocyanine¹⁰. Manganese phthalocyanine is the well known example of square planar manganese(II) complexes. Magnetic properties of the complex have been studied by Lever and coworkers¹⁰. The magnetic moment of the complex is found to be 4.47 B.M. at 300°K and falls to 4.3 B.M. at 107°K. These values have been explained on the basis of an energy level scheme (Fig. 2). The electronic configuration would be orbitally degenerate $(b_{2g})^2 < (e_g)^2 < (a_{1g})^2$ with three unpaired electrons. The observed moment which somewhat is excess of 3.87 B.M. is

 Fig. 2. Energy level diagram for Mn(II) in D_{4h} symmetry.

due to some orbital contribution. The orbital contribution possibly arises through the mixing in

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